

1 **Headland bypassing: Sediment budget dominated by**
2 **moderate rather than extreme events**

3 **Silke Tas^{1,2}, Zoe Hughes¹, Duncan FitzGerald¹, Dangan Xie¹, Tansir Zaman**
4 **Asik¹, Sergio Fagherazzi¹**

5 ¹Department of Earth and Environment, Boston University, Boston, MA, USA

6 ²Hydrology and Environmental Hydraulics, Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, The
7 Netherlands

8 **Key Points:**

- 9 • The sediment budget of an embayment is driven primarily by relatively frequent,
10 just-over-threshold bypassing events, rather than rare extreme events
- 11 • Despite a microtidal regime, tides can modulate the sediment volume deposited
12 inside Slocums Embayment, due to its location at the mouth of Buzzards Bay
- 13 • Climate change will increase bypassing frequency but reduce offshore sediment avail-
14 ability, resulting in either increased or decreased bypassing volumes

Corresponding author: Silke Tas, silke.tas@wur.nl

Abstract

Natural headlands form obstacles to longshore sediment transport between neighbouring coastal cells. Sediment connectivity around headlands only occurs for certain wave and tidal conditions. This study investigates the thresholds and pathways for sediment transport into Slocums Embayment, an enclosed bay situated at the mouth of Buzzards Bay, Massachusetts, USA. The embayment is isolated from the surrounding shoreline by two headlands. A numerical model is validated with field observations and sediment volumes estimated from LIDAR images. Modelling reveals that Slocums Embayment is a completely closed coastal cell under regular conditions, only receiving sediment during storms (return period ≥ 1 year). The cumulative effect of less intense but more frequent storms (once per 1 or 2 years) outweighs the higher rates of sediment transported during the most extreme events. Despite the microtidal regime, tidal currents, possibly enhanced by storm surges that fill and empty Buzzards Bay, control the total volume of sediment deposited inside Slocums Embayment. The impact of climate change on these sediment pathways is twofold: more frequent or larger wave events increase the sediment volumes deposited inside the embayment, while sea-level rise and higher surge levels reduce the availability of offshore sediment for transport. These findings have important implications for coastal management and the prediction of long-term coastal change, as it shifts the focus from the rare, extreme events to the more frequent, moderate events. Understanding the exact thresholds for sediment bypassing, and their associated occurrence probabilities, is key for robust sediment budget calculations.

Plain Language Summary

Headlands are irregular, mostly rocky features that protrude into the sea and become obstacles for the movement of sand along the coast. This study looks at Slocums Embayment, a small, enclosed bay in Buzzards Bay, Massachusetts, USA. Using a computer model and real-world data, we find that, under normal wave conditions, little sand is moved into Slocums Embayment, the process only occurs during high wave conditions that happen once a year or less frequently. Interestingly, even though large waves move more sand, the combined effect of smaller storms that happen often (once every 1 or 2 years) results in more sand moved into the bay. Tidal currents, sometimes together with storm surges, have a major impact on the total amount of sediment moved into Slocums Embayment. Climate change could lead to larger and more frequent storms, which can

47 move more sand into the bay, but rising sea levels might limit how much sand can be
48 picked up from the seabed. These findings are important for managing coastal areas and
49 predicting how coastlines will change over time. Instead of only focusing on rare, extreme
50 events, this research highlights the importance of more frequent, smaller events.

51 **1 Introduction**

52 Approximately half of the world's coastlines are characterised by rocky headlands
53 and embayments (Short & Masselink, 1999), exhibiting high ecological, recreational, and
54 commercial value (King et al., 2021). The sheltering effect of these headlands creates ideal
55 conditions for harbors and pocket beaches. Along irregular shorelines, sediment is often
56 trapped between headlands, forming pocket beaches and embayments (Short & Masselink,
57 1999). In addition to small sediment inputs from rivers, reworking of glacial deposits and
58 cliff erosion, the sediment budget of these coastal cells is a function of headland bypass-
59 ing (Valiente et al., 2019). Headland bypassing is defined as sediment transport around
60 a headland, from one coastal cell to the next (Klein et al., 2020; King et al., 2021). Un-
61 der most conditions, headlands block sediment transport between neighbouring coastal
62 cells, and transport around them occurs only under certain wave and tidal conditions
63 (Klein et al., 2020; Valiente et al., 2019; Short & Masselink, 1999; Vieira da Silva et al.,
64 2018; Cascalho et al., 2014; M. S. Ribeiro, 2017; R. McCarroll et al., 2018; Vieira da Silva
65 et al., 2018). Sediment connectivity, i.e. the pathways and thresholds for sediment trans-
66 port between littoral cells, has been the topic of many studies. For an overview of more
67 than 40 headland bypassing studies, see Klein et al. (2020). Despite several efforts to de-
68 velop conceptual models, e.g., R. J. McCarroll et al. (2021); D. George et al. (2015); D. A. George
69 et al. (2019); Short and Masselink (1999), local studies remain necessary to determine
70 the exact sediment transport thresholds and pathways in and out of most embayments
71 (R. McCarroll et al., 2019; Wishaw et al., 2021).

72 Slocums Embayment, an enclosed bay situated at the mouth of Buzzards Bay, Massachusetts,
73 USA will serve as a case study in this research. While previous headland bypassing stud-
74 ies have focused mostly on Brazil, Australia, Portugal, United Kingdom and the West
75 Coast of the USA, this study is the first to investigate headland bypassing along the North
76 East Coast of the USA. Its location at the mouth of Buzzards Bay creates a unique com-
77 bination of open coast exposure to highly energetic wave conditions generated by extreme
78 storms tracking over the Atlantic Ocean, with tidal currents influenced by the presence

79 of Buzzards Bay. The Slocums/Paskamanset River (the freshwater portion of Slocums
80 River maintained its Native American name (US Geological Survey, 1984)) has histor-
81 ically been heavily polluted. A landfill near Dartmouth, responsible for most of the pol-
82 lution, has been capped off to prevent run-off into the river (Moraff & United States En-
83 vironmental Protection Agency, 2019). Local communities are concerned that contin-
84 ued sediment accumulation near the river mouth could reduce tidal flushing and cause
85 increased water quality issues. Predicting future sedimentation around the inlet requires
86 a better grasp of the sources and pathways of sediment transport into Slocums Embay-
87 ment and an improved understanding of headland bypassing thresholds. Previous stud-
88 ies in this area have been mostly qualitative or focused on individual coastal cells (FitzGerald
89 et al., 1986, 1992).

90 Given the threshold-controlled nature of sediment transport around headlands, most head-
91 land bypassing research has focused on extreme events, e.g., R. McCarroll et al. (2018,
92 2019); Scott et al. (2016); da Silva et al. (2021); Wishaw et al. (2020). For example, R. Mc-
93 Carroll et al. (2019) examined a 1-in-50-year storm, while Harley et al. (2022) analyzed
94 conditions exceeded only once in a 41-year record. However, despite a growing research
95 focus on headland bypassing, no studies have compared the relative importance of ex-
96 treme events versus more frequent, just-over-threshold bypassing events in driving the
97 sediment budget of an embayment. Here, we define extreme events as rare storms with
98 long return periods (typically >10–50 years), and moderate events as more frequent con-
99 ditions that just exceed the threshold for bypassing. Because thresholds vary by head-
100 land, the exact return periods differ locally, meaning our distinction is based on occur-
101 rence frequency rather than absolute wave height. Wolman and Miller (1960) showed that
102 for geomorphic processes, there exists an optimal frequency at which the product of event
103 frequency and the amount of “work” done on the landscape (in this case, sediment trans-
104 port around the headland) reaches a maximum. This study applies that concept to head-
105 land bypassing, testing whether the sediment budget of an enclosed embayment is pri-
106 marily driven by rare, extreme events or by more frequent, moderate events.

107 This study aims to map sediment pathways and quantify thresholds for headland bypass-
108 ing around Barneys Joy Point into Slocums River Embayment. We use a numerical model
109 (see also Xie et al. (2024a)), validated with field observations and LIDAR-derived sed-
110 iment volumes to simulate a range of idealised and realistic storm scenarios. By linking
111 storm return periods to transport volumes, we assess whether the sediment budget of

112 Slocums Embayment is primarily shaped by rare, extreme storms (e.g., 1/50-year storm)
113 or by more frequent, moderate events (e.g., a yearly storm). More broadly, this study
114 tests the applicability of frequency-magnitude concepts to headland bypassing and pro-
115 vides a framework for evaluating sediment connectivity in embayed coasts worldwide.
116 Understanding headland bypassing dynamics is crucial for robust sediment budget cal-
117 culations, and hence valuable knowledge for coastal management and predicting long-
118 term coastal change (da Silva et al., 2023; Woodroffe et al., 2022; R. J. McCarroll et al.,
119 2021; Wishaw et al., 2021; Valiente et al., 2019; Cooper et al., 2002; Motyka & Bramp-
120 ton, 1993; Vieira da Silva et al., 2016; D. A. George et al., 2019).

121 **2 Methods**

122 Sediment transport in the vicinity of Slocums Embayment is explored using a cou-
123 pled Delft3D-FLOW/WAVE model. Delft3D-FLOW solves the unsteady shallow water
124 equations (Lesser et al., 2004) and Delft3D-WAVE uses the third-generation numerical
125 wave model SWAN (Booij et al., 1999). Delft3D has been successfully used for sediment
126 transport simulations around headlands (Vieira da Silva et al., 2016; R. McCarroll et al.,
127 2018; D. A. George et al., 2019; King et al., 2021; Valiente et al., 2019). A full descrip-
128 tion and validation of the model set-up can be found in Xie et al. (2024a). A short de-
129 scription of the model set-up, validation and scenarios (representing different storm con-
130 ditions) is provided below. Model boundary conditions are derived from the North At-
131 lantic Coast Comprehensive Study (NACCS), a coastal storm wave and water level mod-
132 elling study of the US North Atlantic coast (Cialone et al., 2015). NACCS was validated
133 at three levels (Atlantic Ocean to regional scale) for 22 historical storm events and pro-
134 duced joint probability of coastal storm environmental forcing parameters along the en-
135 tire US North Atlantic Coast (Cialone et al., 2015). Sediment volume changes of the spit
136 at the Slocums River Inlet based on a series of LIDAR DEMs were used to validate the
137 modelled morphological changes.

138 **2.1 Study Area**

139 Northwestern Buzzards Bay in Massachusetts, USA (Figure 1a), is a complex coastal
140 system consisting of multiple headlands, producing several coastal cells containing tidal
141 inlets and mixed-sediment beaches. While these compartments form mostly closed sed-
142 iment cells during regular wave conditions, high-energy events like severe winter storms

143 or rare tropical storms can generate sediment pulses past headlands (FitzGerald et al.,
144 1992). Near the mouth of Buzzards Bay, Slocums River Embayment is delimited by Mishaum
145 Point to the east and Barneys Joy Point to the west (see Figure 1b). The embayment
146 shoreline is dominated by gravel and bedrock, except on the inner western side of Slocums
147 River inlet, where sandy beaches, a spit and a series of beach ridges are present. The beach
148 ridges represent historic positions of the shoreline, as it progressed seaward. Aerial im-
149 ages covering the last 30 years (1991-2021, Figure 1c-f) show a dynamic spit system grad-
150 ually accumulating sand. Since Slocums River drains a small basin, and has a small dis-
151 charge of ca. $5 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ (US Geological Survey, 2023), the sediment accumulating near Slocums
152 River inlet is likely marine in origin, entering the embayment via headland bypassing.
153 Moreover, the sand within Slocums Embayment is highly quartz-rich, well-sorted and
154 individual quartz grains are well rounded.

155

156 At the mouth of Buzzards Bay, the tidal regime is semi-diurnal and microtidal, with a
157 tidal range between 0.7-1.3 m (neap and spring tides respectively, based on NOAA tidal
158 station in Newport, RI (station 8452660)). There is little tidal amplification in Buzzards
159 Bay, since the natural period of the bay (2-3 hours) is substantially less than the M2 pe-
160 riod (Signell, 1987). Offshore, the average wave height is approximately 1.0 m with a peak
161 wave period of 7.1 s (at NDBC offshore station (station 44085 and BUZM3)). The shore-
162 line is only exposed to waves approaching from the south to southwest. Due to the low
163 wave and tidal energy, it has generally been assumed that infrequent, large-magnitude
164 events (hurricanes) may have a large impact on the overall morphological patterns in the
165 embayment (FitzGerald et al., 1992).

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2.2 Model set-up

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168 For this study, two separate grids were developed: a larger one for the WAVE cal-
169 culations (dashed line in Figure 2), and a smaller FLOW grid nested inside the WAVE
170 domain (solid line in Figure 2). The southern boundary of the WAVE domain is located
171 offshore to avoid strong bed level gradients at the boundary and to avoid any shelter-
172 ing effects of the nearby islands. Its position was chosen close to output point 9740 of
173 the NACCS model (green square marker in Figure 2), facilitating the use of NACCS re-
174 sults as input to our simulations. The lateral boundaries of the WAVE domain were se-
lected so that wave shadow zones would not affect the region of interest around Slocums

Figure 1. (a) Location of the area of interest in Northwestern Buzzards Bay, South Massachusetts, USA. The red rectangle indicates the location of panel b. (b) Slocums Embayment at the mouth of Buzzards Bay, bounded by two headlands: Barneys Joy Point and Mishaum Point. West of Barneys Joy Point is Allens Beach and Allens Pond. The red rectangle indicates the location of panels c-f. (c-f) Temporal evolution of the spit at Slocums River inlet, in 1991, 2001, 2012 and 2021 (images from Google Earth). The polygons in panel f divide the spit into 4 regions for which the volume changes are determined using LIDAR images, see Figure 4).

175 Embayment. The orthogonal grid varies from 80 m grid cell size near the boundaries to
 176 40 m in the region of interest.
 177 The FLOW domain was extended far enough south to capture flow into and out of Buz-
 178 zards Bay. The lateral boundaries extend slightly beyond the region of interest, and the
 179 northern boundary allows for the inclusion of a reasonable tidal prism inside the Slocums
 180 and Westport Rivers. Along the southern boundary, a water level is prescribed based
 181 on the water level at output point 9088 in the NACCS ADCIRC model. A velocity bound-
 182 ary condition is applied to the eastern and western FLOW domain boundaries, based

Figure 2. Delft3D model domains for WAVE (dashed black rectangle) and FLOW (solid black rectangle). The NACCS output points (Cialone et al., 2015) that serve as boundary conditions are indicated by the markers, with the color representing the type of output (orange triangles: velocity, yellow dot: water level, green squares: waves and wind). Measuring stations (S1-S5) are visualised with purple asterisks.

183 on linear interpolation between NACCS output points 10414, 1219, 9143, 1003, 9086, 1275,
 184 8967 (counterclockwise, starting along the west boundary). The model was run in depth-
 185 averaged mode.

186 The bathymetry is based on the Continuously Updated Digital Elevation Model (CIRES,
 187 2014; Amante et al., 2023). This bathymetry was validated with point measurements col-
 188 lected in September 2022 (see Figure S1). The boundary conditions for the different sce-
 189 narios are based on annual exceedance probability curves for wave heights and water lev-
 190 els from NACCS, see Table 1. The river discharge boundary conditions used in the anal-

191 ysis are based on a stream gauge located in Paskamanset River (gauge 01105933, US Ge-
192 ological Survey (2023)).

193 Sediment transport is calculated using the sediment transport formulations of Van Rijn
194 (2007), TRANSPOR2004. A single sediment fraction is included in the model, medium
195 sand with a D50 of 350 μm , based on sediment samples (see dots in Figure 3a, as well
196 as Supplementary Text S2 and Folk (1966)). While using a multi-fraction sediment trans-
197 port model could provide additional insights, e.g., headlands can act as a natural filter
198 and contribute to grain size sorting (Cascalho et al., 2014), it would also require signif-
199 icantly greater computational effort. Given the scope of this study, testing different hy-
200 drodynamic boundary conditions was prioritized, as this is expected to be the primary
201 control on morphological changes in this system.

202 The spatial distribution of sediment in the model domain is based on a sediment tex-
203 ture map by Foster et al. (2016). All patches that contained predominantly sand were
204 included as sandy patches in the model (see blue colors in Figure 3a). The sand cover-
205 age derived from this map was checked against our field samples and an alternative method
206 developed by King et al. (2021), using the smoothness of a high-resolution bathymetry
207 as an indicator of loose sediment (see Supplementary Text S2). In our model, the sand
208 was divided into 5 geographic zones. Even though the sediment properties are the same
209 across all 5 zones, this separation in 5 zones allows us to trace the source of the sediment
210 deposited inside Slocums Embayment. The first zone is Allens Beach (yellow patch in
211 Figure 3b), which includes the intertidal beach and supratidal dunes east and west of
212 Allens Pond inlet. Towards the headlands on each side, the beach composition changes
213 to gravel; the extent of the sandy patch in the model is based on field observations and
214 sediment samples. The second zone is the nearshore area in front of Allens Pond (orange
215 patch in Figure 3b), surrounded by patches of bedrock. The third zone (pink) represents
216 the sediment inside Slocums Embayment, delimited by Barneys Joy Point on the west
217 and Mishaum Point on the east. The offshore sediment is divided into a westerly (ma-
218 genta) and easterly (purple) zone, separated by a bedrock outcrop south of Barneys Joy
219 Point. The sediment thickness of the 4 submerged sediment zones is set to 2 m, while
220 the sediment thickness of the Allens Beach patch is set to 0.5 m.

Figure 3. (a) Sediment type based on USGS sediment texture map of Buzzards Bay (Foster et al. (2016)), in blue shades). Median grain size based on sediment samples from this study in yellow-brown dots. (b) Sediment zones implemented in the model. Darkest color is bedrock (i.e., no sediment available in the model), all other zones contain medium sand.

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2.3 Model scenarios

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Different wave and water level conditions are explored through multiple idealised model scenarios. The peak significant wave height (H_s) and wind speed (u_{10}) for four return periods (1, 2, 10 and 50 years) are derived from the annual exceedance probability curves at NACCS output point 9740, near the offshore WAVE boundary (green marker in Figure 2). The wave period (T_p) corresponding to each wave height is calculated using a linear relationship between wave height and wave period at the offshore NACCS output location (green square in Figure 2), based on 100 storms reported in the NACCS database. The wave and wind conditions are kept constant throughout each simulation.

Return period [yr]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	u_{10} [m/s]
1	4.7	11.6	12.8
2	6.2	12.3	15.9
10	9.5	13.8	22.6
50	12.4	15.1	28.6

Table 1. Offshore peak wave and wind conditions for storms with different return periods (based on NACCS exceedance probability curves, Cialone et al. (2015)).

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231 Due to the orientation of the coastline and the presence of offshore islands (see Figure
 232 2), our project area is only exposed to waves coming from south to southwest. There-
 233 fore, only three wave directions are considered in the simulations: 180°, 210° and 240°.
 234 Three water level scenarios are developed to assess the influence of tides and storms: con-
 235 stant water level (MSL, no tide or storm surge), tide-only and tide + storm surge. The
 236 latter two scenarios are derived from a NACCS storm time series. Combining 4 storm
 237 strengths, 3 wave directions and 3 water level scenarios results in 36 model scenarios (Ta-
 238 ble 2). In each scenario, the wave conditions are constant in time, only the water level
 239 varies in the tide-only and tide + storm surge simulations. A constant, spatially uniform
 240 wind field is applied to the model domain. This approach allows us to isolate the impact
 241 of each storm characteristic (wave height, direction and surge) on headland bypassing.
 242 In addition to these 36 idealised storm scenarios, two additional scenarios were simulated:
 243 an idealised non-storm, low-wave scenario which occurs multiple times per year ($H_S =$
 244 1.5 m), and a realistic storm scenario. The low-wave scenario conditions are based on
 245 field observations (see next section) and are used to test the hypothesis that Slocums Em-
 246 bayment does not receive sediment during regular conditions. The realistic storm sce-
 247 nario is based on a representative storm from the NACCS dataset of hypothetical hur-
 248 ricanes, whose storm track follows a path similar to the 1938 hurricane. The 1938 hur-
 249 ricane significantly impacted the area and is the storm of record for the southeastern coast
 250 of Connecticut, Rhode Island, and Western Buzzards Bay. The hypothetical hurricane
 251 has a peak wave height of 9 m and peak storm surge levels of 3.5 m above MSL which
 252 preceded the peak wave conditions. This realistic storm scenario will be used to study
 the effect of the time-varying wave and water level conditions.

Storm return periods [yr]	1, 2, 10, 50
Wave direction [°]	180, 210, 240
Water level	MSL, tide-only, tide + surge

Table 2. Overview of the 36 model scenarios with all combinations of storm return period (4), wave direction (3) and water level (3) scenario. Wave direction is defined according to the nautical convention (180° waves are coming from the south).

2.4 Model validation

The model was validated using three approaches (see Supplementary Text S3 for more detail). First, modelled water levels and wave conditions were compared with observations during typical winter conditions. Second, model output was compared to NACCS data at several output points within the model domain during extreme storm conditions (see also (Xie et al., 2024a)). Third, a hybrid validation combined NACCS-derived velocity boundary conditions with observed water level, wave, and wind boundary conditions to compare modelled and observed velocities during typical winter conditions.

Observations at 5 locations in the model domain (stations S1-S5 in Figure 2) were recorded between October and December 2022, using the following instruments: 1. Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) with wave gauge (stations S1 and S2), 2. wave gauge (S3), 3. ADCP (S4), and 4. pressure sensor (S5). For the first validation approach, a period coincident with a higher wave energy was selected: 8-15 November 2022 (see Figure S4), while the third validation window was selected based on the tide: 24-28 December 2022 (see Figure S5). The comparison between modelled and observed values was quantified by using the skill score as proposed by Willmott (1981).

In the first validation approach, simulated and observed water levels and wave conditions agreed well during typical winter conditions (skill scores 0.70-0.99). Modelled velocity magnitudes were of the correct order and captured the general trends, although the skill score was relatively low (0.13-0.47). At locations S1 and S2, the modelled velocity direction lacked the distinct tidal signature present in the observations, likely due to the use of Neumann boundary conditions along the east and west FLOW domain boundaries, where observed velocity data was unavailable. As a result, while water levels and waves were well captured, tidal exchange with Buzzards Bay was not, limiting the model's ability to reproduce the observed tidal velocities. The following two validation approaches apply velocity boundary conditions to improved the modelled velocity performance.

The second validation approach tested model performance under extreme storm conditions, using NACCS-derived boundary conditions (including velocities along the east and west FLOW boundaries). Xie et al. (2024a) compared the output of our model with several NACCS output points located in our model domain and showed good agreement for water levels, waves and current velocities (skill score > 0.7). Some differences between our model and NACCS outputs, particularly in the nearshore region, can be attributed

286 to our model's higher spatial resolution and the use of more recent bathymetric data in
287 these areas.

288 The third, hybrid validation approach combined NACCS tidal velocity time series (from
289 the tide-only scenario) along the east and west boundaries with observed water level and
290 wave boundary conditions along the south boundary. Including tidal velocity boundary
291 conditions significantly improved the modelled current patterns at location S2, reveal-
292 ing a clear tidal pattern in contrast to the uni-directional flow in the Neumann bound-
293 ary conditions case). The current pattern at location S1 showed less impact of the tidal
294 velocity boundary conditions. However, Xie et al. (2024b) demonstrated that Gooseberry
295 Island, located between S1 and S2 and connected to the mainland via a reinforced tombolo,
296 separates the flow into two distinct circulation cells with minimal sediment connectiv-
297 ity. Therefore, reduced model skill on the western side of the domain is not expected to
298 impact the dynamics around Slocums Embayment. While the skill score for velocity mag-
299 nitude improved, it was still lower than the scores for water level and wave height (0.4-
300 0.6), likely because the applied tidal velocity boundary conditions were taken from a dif-
301 ferent time and may have deviated slightly from actual conditions.

302 Together, these three validation approaches demonstrate that the model reliably sim-
303 ulates water levels and waves under normal, storm and extreme storm conditions. Ac-
304 curately reproducing velocity patterns in the eastern part of the FLOW domain, how-
305 ever, requires applying tidal velocity boundary conditions to represent the tidal exchange
306 with Buzzards Bay.

307 Finally, we have also performed a sensitivity analysis on the median grain size, as our
308 selected value of $350\ \mu\text{m}$ is on the coarser end of the sediment found at Slocums River
309 Inlet. For a storm with a return period of 10 years, a wave direction of 210° , and a con-
310 stant water level, the instantaneous sediment volume change with a D50 of $200\ \mu\text{m}$ in-
311 creases to $450\ \text{m}^3/\text{hr}$ (compared to $405\ \text{m}^3/\text{hr}$ for $350\ \mu\text{m}$). This variation, while expected,
312 remains within the same order of magnitude.

313 **2.5 Sediment volume estimates from LIDAR-derived morphological changes**

314 Aerial images dating back to 1938 suggest that Slocums inlet has gained sediment.
315 However, it is only since 2005 that LIDAR data allow us to quantify the sediment vol-
316 ume change around Slocums inlet (OCM Partners, 2009, 2010, 2013, 2015b, 2018). The
317 earlier LIDAR-derived DEMs stopped at the water surface, and therefore were taken around

low tide to include as much as possible of the emerged part of the spit. To allow consistent comparison with these older data sets, the lowest elevation that was included in all LIDAR DEMs was -0.4 m NAVD88 (MLW is -0.58 m NAVD88 at NOAA Newport, RI station). The images were corrected for differences in Geoid used for processing the raw data (see Supplementary Text S4). The western side of the river inlet was divided into 4 polygons (see Figure 1f and Supplementary Figure S6), and for each LIDAR DEM, the volume above -0.4 m NAVD88 was calculated.

3 Results

3.1 Net sediment volume estimates from LIDAR-derived morphological changes

Figure 4a-f shows that a pulse of sediment has moved north along the shoreline between 2005 and 2018, accumulating in the northernmost polygon, i.e., nearest the river inlet. This is also confirmed by the volume of each subpolygon in Figure 4g. Initially, the two southern polygons (blue and orange), i.e., closest to the headland, contained most sediment, gradually losing material to the northern polygons (yellow and purple), i.e., closest to the river mouth. The last two LIDAR images show that only the northern polygon, nearest the river mouth, is still gaining sediment, while the three southern polygons maintain a stable volume. Over a period of 13 years, the spit system gained a volume of ca. 33700 m³ (Figure 4h), with an average gain of approximately 2600 m³/year.

3.2 Threshold for sediment transport into Slocums Embayment

Figure 5 shows the currents (vector field) and maximum bed shear stresses (colormap) at 4 different time steps over the tidal cycle (rows: 6 hours before high tide, 3 hours before high tide, high tide and 3 hours after high tide) for 3 different wave conditions (columns). The left column represents a tide-only scenario, the middle column a non-storm, low-wave scenario ($H_s = 1.5\text{m}$), which occurs regularly (exceeded 12% of the time) and the right column represents storm wave conditions occurring once every 10 years (see Table 1).

For tide-only and low-wave conditions (top two rows in Figure 5, panels a-h), the flow completely bypasses Slocums Embayment (as seen from the vector field), and the bed shear stresses are too low within most of the domain to suspend sediment (the critical

Figure 4. (a-f) Evolution of the spit volume near the inlet of Slocums River between 2005 and 2018, based on LIDAR (see Figure 1f for the location of the spit and the polygons), (g) total volume of the spit above -0.4m NAVD88, separated in four sub-volumes along the shore (see panels a-f for division subvolumes), and (h) total volume change of the spit compared to initial volume in 2005.

348 bed shear stress for erosion is 0.21 N/m^2 for a D_{50} of $350 \mu\text{m}$). The current patterns are
 349 similar for the tide-only and low-wave scenarios, which implies that, under relatively calm
 350 conditions, the currents are dominated by the tidal filling and emptying of Buzzards Bay.
 351 It is only under storm conditions (bottom row Figure 5, panel i-l) that the flow curves
 352 around Barneys Joy Point, opening a pathway for sediment transport into Slocums Em-
 353 bayment. This confirms that sediment transport into Slocums Embayment is event-driven
 354 and only occurs during storms, when the wave-driven currents are large enough to mod-
 355 ify the tidal flow in and out of Buzzards Bay.

356 3.3 Scenario analysis

357 The 36 scenarios are run for 72 hours, of which the first 24 hours are morphostatic
 358 spin-up, followed by 48 hours of morphodynamic simulation. Figure 6 shows the result-
 359 ing sediment fluxes (vector field) and bed level changes (colormap) for the tide-only sce-

Figure 5. Current patterns (vector field) and maximum bed shear stress (colormap) under 3 different wave conditions. Left column: tide-only, middle column: low-wave scenario ($H_s = 1.5$ m), and right column: 1 in 10-year wave conditions ($H_s = 9.5$ m). The rows represent different time steps in the tidal cycle: from 6 hours before high tide to 3 hours after high tide. Note that the vectors in the right column have been scaled for clarity purposes, the scale is given in the top left corner of each frame.

360 narios (4 storm strengths, rows, and 3 wave directions, columns). Most of the sediment
 361 transported into the embayment during a storm is deposited just around the headland.
 362 The volume of sediment deposited near the headland increases with wave height, and
 363 is lowest for waves coming from the south (180° , left column in Figure 6).

Figure 6. Residual sediment fluxes (vector field) and bed level changes (colormap) under different wave conditions. The rows show different return periods of the wave height and wind speed (ranging from 1 to 50 years). The columns represent different wave directions (180° , 210° , and 240°). For clarity, the vector scale changes among wave conditions, see arrow in top left corner of each panel.

364 While sustained peak storm conditions lasting 48 hours are highly unlikely, this approach
 365 was adopted such that the tide-only and tide + storm surge scenarios could be compared
 366 to the constant water level scenario. At the end of each scenario, the change in sediment
 367 volume inside Slocums Embayment is calculated, where Slocums Embayment is delin-
 368 eated by a fictional line between the headlands of Barneys Joy Point and Mishaum Point
 369 (following the same line that separates the sediment fractions of Slocums Embayment
 370 and East offshore in Figure 3). This sediment volume is then divided by the duration

371 of the storm (48 hours) to obtain an average hourly net sediment volume change, see Equa-
 372 tion 1:

$$Q_i = \frac{\Delta V_{Slocums}}{\Delta t_{storm}} \quad (1)$$

373 Where Q_i is the average hourly net sediment volume change [m^3/hr], $\Delta V_{Slocums}$ is the
 374 total sediment volume change inside Slocums Embayment [m^3] and Δt_{storm} is the storm
 375 duration [hr].

376 In Figure 7 the average hourly net sediment volume change is plotted for each scenario,
 377 with the wave height on the horizontal axis (and the corresponding return period on the
 378 secondary horizontal axis at the top of the figure). The origin of the sediment deposited
 379 into Slocums Embayment is traced back to the different source regions in Figure 8b-f.

380 Higher waves generate more net transport into the embayment, although this relation-
 381 ship is weaker for waves coming from the south (180° , blue markers). For the lower wave
 382 heights, a wave direction of 210° generates the highest net transport, however for extreme
 383 storms the westerly waves generate more net transport. While the gross transport into
 384 the embayment increases with wave height for all wave directions, a transport pathway
 385 out of the embayment opens up for higher waves coming from 180 - 210° , reducing the net
 transport in these scenarios (see Figure 8d).

Figure 7. Average hourly net sediment volume change (Q_i) into Slocums Embayment for all 36 scenarios. The bottom horizontal axis gives the peak wave height (H_s) of each scenario, the top horizontal axis the corresponding return period (T_r). The symbols represent water level scenarios and the colors wave direction.

386 In nearly all wave height and direction combinations, net morphological change is smaller
 387 in the tide-only scenario compared to the constant water level scenario. This is due to
 388 two factors: (1) the fluctuating water levels modulate sediment transport, and (2) some
 389 sediment that enters the embayment is later transported out again by strong tidal cur-
 390 rents. The only exception occurs in the lowest wave height scenario, where the tide +
 391 storm surge condition results in greater morphological change than the scenarios with-
 392 out storm surge. However it should be noted that in these hypothetical scenarios, the
 393 wave height is constant in time. In reality, the timing of the peak wave conditions with
 394 respect to the surge will have a significant impact on sediment transport, resulting in
 395 larger or smaller morphological change. For example, Costa et al. (2019) showed that
 396 for a microtidal headland setting in Brazil, non-linear wave-tide interactions increased
 397 bypassing rates.

398 Although larger waves transport more sediment, the storms generating these larger waves
 399 occur less frequently, as seen in Figure 7 (secondary x-axis). Consequently, a cumula-
 400 tive sediment volume change was calculated, which incorporates the hourly net sediment
 401 volume change and the annual exceedance probability of the corresponding wave con-
 402 ditions, see Equation 2:

$$Q_c = \frac{\Delta V_{Slocums}}{\Delta t_{storm} * T_r} \quad (2)$$

403 Where Q_c is the cumulative sediment volume change [$m^3/hr/yr$] and T_r is the return pe-
 404 riod of the wave conditions [yr].

405 Figure 8a shows that a storm with a return period of 2 years and wave direction 210° is
 406 responsible for most net sediment volume increase in the embayment over longer time
 407 scales. While the 1 in 50-year wave conditions will generate most net sediment volume
 408 increase per hour, these conditions are so rare that their total contribution to sediment
 409 deposition inside Slocums Embayment is minor. Note that a positive sediment volume
 410 change indicates sediment import into Slocums Embayment, whereas the negative val-
 411 ues in Figure 8d correspond to sediment export. However, these rates of sediment loss
 412 never exceed the total sediment import from the other regions, thus leading to net pos-
 413 itive volume changes for all scenarios.

414 The sediment in Slocums Embayment at the end of each 48-hour storm simulation is traced
 415 back to its region of origin (Figure 8b-f). Even though Allens Beach and the nearshore
 416 area of Allens Pond represent only a small portion of the entire model domain, together

Figure 8. Cumulative sediment volume change, i.e. the average hourly net sediment volume change divided by the return period (see Equation 2). The sediment volume change inside Slocums Embayment (a) is split up into the contributions of each region of origin (b-f), the colored outlines corresponding to the patches in Figure 3b. The shapes represent water level scenarios and the colors wave directions.

417 they are responsible for more than half of the sediment that ends up in Slocums Embay-
 418 ment. Allens Beach provides the most sediment under westerly waves in scenarios with
 419 surge, since the westerly waves generate the strongest longshore currents and the surge
 420 allows the waves to erode sediment from the upper beach and dune foot. The largest con-
 421 tributions from the Allens Pond nearshore zone occur for a wave direction of 210°, be-
 422 cause although 240° generates the strongest longshore currents, Gooseberry Island shel-
 423 ters the more westerly waves, resulting in lower wave heights nearshore, and therefore
 424 less erosion.

425 **3.4 Realistic storm scenario**

426 Figure 9b shows the instantaneous sediment volume change inside Slocums Em-
 427 bayment (dashed line), divided into the contributions of each sediment region (different
 colors). Figure 9c gives the cumulative volume change inside the embayment.

Figure 9. (a) Left y-axes: wave height (blue) and wave direction (green), right axis: water level (orange) during a NACCS hypothetical hurricane. Instantaneous (b) and cumulative (c) sediment volume change inside Slocums Embayment (dashed black line) and split up into the contributions of each region of origin (same colours as in Figures 3b and 8).

428
 429 3700 m³ of sediment is deposited inside Slocums Embayment during the storm, most of
 430 which was eroded from Allens Beach and Allens Pond (yellow and orange lines in Fig-
 431 ure 9b-c) and transported around Barneys Joy Point by headland bypassing. The pink
 432 line (sediment originally inside Slocums Embayment) shows that during the peak of the
 433 storm surge, the conditions inside the embayment are energetic enough to erode 3300
 434 m³ of sediment, which is then exported out of the embayment. In fact, around t = 45
 435 hours, there is a strong sediment flux out of the embayment, due to a combination of high
 436 wave energy and ebb tide. The net effect of these two sediment pathways (headland by-
 437 passing and cross-shore transport) is a sediment deposition of 500 m³ inside Slocums Em-
 438 bayment.

4 Discussion

4.1 Moderate vs. extreme storms at other headlands

Traditionally, the sediment budget of enclosed embayments has often been treated as a closed coastal cell, without any exchange of sediment with neighbouring coastal cells (van Rijn, 2010; Hsu & Evans, 1989). Over the last 30 years, an increasing number of studies have described processes of headland bypassing (Short & Masselink, 1999; Smith, 2001; Goodwin et al., 2013; M. Ribeiro et al., 2014; Duarte et al., 2014; bin Ab Razak, 2015; Vieira da Silva et al., 2016), and showed that headland bypassing may be more widespread than previously assumed (Valiente et al., 2019). These studies have focused on identifying the wave and tidal conditions producing headland bypassing, see e.g., Costa et al. (2019); King et al. (2021); R. McCarroll et al. (2018); Valiente et al. (2019); Vieira da Silva et al. (2018). These conditions generally occur during extreme events (R. McCarroll et al., 2018, 2019; Scott et al., 2016; da Silva et al., 2021; Wishaw et al., 2020). The current study, however, reveals that morphological change in Slocums Embayment is dominated by small volumes deposited during frequent storms (occurring every 1-5 years), rather than the larger volume moved into the embayment during rare extreme events, as illustrated in Figure 10a-b. King et al. (2021) modelled bypassing rates around 29 headlands in Cornwall, UK under various wave and tide conditions. Combining these bypassing rates and their corresponding exceedance probabilities (see Supplementary Text S5) allowed us to test whether the sediment budget of enclosed embayments are driven by moderate rather than extreme conditions, see Table 3.

Scenario	Number	Percentage
Total scenarios	348	100%
Scenarios with sediment deposited inside embayment	311/348	89%
Bypassing under large and extreme waves (no bypassing median waves)	119/311	38%
Most instantaneous bypassing under extreme waves	116/119	97%
Most cumulative bypassing under large waves	90/116	78%

Table 3. Analysis of the headland bypassing rates calculated by King et al. (2021), see also Supplementary Text S5.

459

460

Figure 10. Boxplot of the instantaneous (Q_i , left column) and cumulative (Q_c , right column) headland bypassing rates in Slocums Embayment (top row) and in the study of King et al. (2021) (bottom row). Note that the absolute values of Slocums Embayment and King et al. (2021) cannot be compared one-on-one, due to different definitions of the bypassing rates (sediment deposited in embayment vs. sediment passing through headland transect) and frequency (return period peak value vs. hourly exceedance probability), hence the bypassing rates of King et al. (2021) are denoted by Q^* .

461 King et al. (2021) calculated headland bypassing rates for three wave conditions: me-
 462 dian waves (wave height exceeded 50% of the time), large waves (exceedance probabili-
 463 ty 5%) and extreme waves (exceedance probability 0.14%). These 3 wave conditions were
 464 applied to 348 different scenarios (29 headlands, 2 water levels, 3 wave directions, wave-

465 only and wave+tide). Sediment deposition inside the embayment occurred in 89% of these
466 scenarios, but only 119 scenarios are considered as true headland bypassing cases (where
467 the headland blocks all sediment transport during regular conditions, and bypassing oc-
468 curs only during large and/or extreme wave conditions). Almost all bypassing cases (97%)
469 had the highest instantaneous bypassing rates during the highest waves (see Figure 10c).
470 Interestingly, in 78% of those simulations, the large waves contributed more to the cu-
471 mulative bypassing volumes than the extreme waves (see Figure 10d). This corroborates
472 findings of the current study, that the sediment budget of an embayment enclosed by head-
473 lands is driven by frequent, moderate storms rather than rare, extreme events.

474 **4.2 Timing and storm history**

475 This study assumed constant wave conditions to facilitate comparison between sce-
476 narios. In reality, the wave height varies over time during a storm. Due to the location
477 of the embayment at the mouth of Buzzards Bay, the filling and emptying of the bay has
478 a large impact on the resulting sediment transport patterns. Based on a database of 100
479 historical storms (Cialone et al., 2015), peak surge levels usually precede peak wave con-
480 ditions (see Figure 11). Moreover, storms with the highest waves (i.e., the upper quar-
481 tile with peak wave heights exceeding 10 m) are over-represented in storms with a time
482 lag between 3 and 9 hours between peak water level and peak wave height. This further
483 illustrates that in this region, peak wave conditions and peak water levels often do not
484 coincide.

485 As illustrated by the realistic storm scenario, peak wave conditions following the peak
486 water level may result in higher rates of sediment export from the embayment and con-
487 sequently lower rates of net sediment deposition. Therefore, the sediment volume changes
488 based on constant wave conditions likely represent the upper limit of expected sediment
489 volumes deposited in Slocums Embayment.

490 Extreme events not only produce large direct bypassing volumes during the storm, but
491 the sequencing of different wave conditions or multiple storm events can also trigger by-
492 passing at a later moment. As a result, there may not always be a single threshold for
493 headland bypassing at certain locations. Sedimentation on the updrift side of the head-
494 land can lower the bypassing threshold (Wishaw et al., 2021), or even allow ‘leaking’,
495 i.e., bypassing under modal conditions (da Silva et al., 2021; Da Silva et al., 2025). The
496 opposite could also be true, when a bypassing event has depleted the updrift embayment,

Figure 11. Histogram of the time lag between peak water level and peak wave height for a database of 100 historical storms (Cialone et al., 2015). A positive time lag corresponds to the peak water level preceding the peak wave height. The stacked bars represent the quartile distribution of the wave heights (blue) and water levels (brown) in each histogram bin.

497 the threshold for bypassing may temporarily increase, or require a specific sequence of
 498 wave directions to make sediment available for a new headland bypassing pulse (Wishaw
 499 et al., 2021).

500 To allow comparison between scenarios, all scenarios used the same initial conditions.
 501 As a consequence, it was not possible to analyse the complete effect of storm history on
 502 sediment availability and build-up. However, each scenario was modelled for 48 hours
 503 of constant wave conditions. During this period, some sediment build-up and depletion
 504 may have occurred, particularly around Allens Beach, where the initial sediment thick-
 505 ness was only 0.5 m, and under certain scenarios, portions of the beach and dune sys-
 506 tem experienced severe erosion.

507 Together, our findings and those of King et al. (2021); Da Silva et al. (2025) highlight
 508 that wave thresholds for bypassing must be considered alongside their frequency of oc-
 509 currence and preceding storm history, the latter being particularly important at head-
 510 lands with multiple bypassing pathways. Understanding both the thresholds and recur-
 511 rence of bypassing events is therefore essential for accurate sediment budget assessments
 512 and effective coastal management.

513 **4.3 LIDAR as an alternative to field observations during extreme events**

514 One of the challenges of studying headland bypassing and sediment dynamics near
 515 headlands is the lack of field observations during extreme conditions. Previous studies,
 516 e.g., Backstrom et al. (2015); Harley et al. (2022); da Silva et al. (2023), used detailed
 517 pre- and post-storm bathymetries to investigate morphological change on headland-bounded
 518 beaches. However, detailed topo-bathymetric surveys are often not available. This study
 519 proposes an alternative method to validate sediment volume changes. Given that Slocums
 520 Embayment is a closed littoral cell most of the time (see Figure 5) and Slocums River
 521 has a nearly negligible discharge, we assumed that the sediment accumulating at Slocums
 522 River Inlet could be linked to headland bypassing. The modelled average hourly net de-
 523 position rates inside the embayment ($O(10^2 \text{ m}^3/\text{hr})$, see Figure 7) result in cumulative
 524 volumes of $O(10^3 \text{ m}^3/\text{yr})$ when integrated over a typical storm duration of 6-12 hours.
 525 This is the same order of magnitude as the average yearly volume increase of the spit
 526 at the inlet of Slocums River, derived from LIDAR images ($O(10^3 \text{ m}^3)$, see Figure 4).

527 **4.4 Will headland bypassing increase or decrease due to climate change?**

528 It is generally predicted that climate change will increase storm intensity and fre-
 529 quency (Lin et al., 2012), also along the east coast of the US (Villarini & Vecchi, 2013).
 530 This will increase the exceedance probability of peak wave conditions, while slower mov-
 531 ing storm systems (Kossin, 2018) could generate higher storm surge levels. More frequent
 532 extreme wave conditions will increase the cumulative sediment deposition inside Slocums
 533 Embayment, while higher storm waves may even further increase headland bypassing (Xie
 534 et al., 2024a). However, the relationship with increasing surge levels is not straightfor-
 535 ward. On one hand, higher water levels may erode previously inaccessible sand in the
 536 dunes between Allens Pond and Barneys Joy Point. On the other hand, higher water lev-
 537 els move the depth of closure (see also Valiente et al. (2019)) line closer to shore, poten-
 538 tially preventing sand from offshore being picked up, and thus reducing the volume of
 539 sand available for headland bypassing. This complex response to water level is also con-
 540 firmed by King et al. (2021), with some headlands experiencing higher bypassing rates
 541 around spring high water, whereas bypassing rates were higher around spring low wa-
 542 ter for other headlands.

5 Conclusion

Slocums Embayment is a sediment sink at the mouth of Buzzards Bay. Based on LIDAR images, the spit near the river inlet is accumulating ca. 2600 m³ sand per year. A numerical model (Delft3D) was used to analyse the thresholds and pathways of sediment into Slocums Embayment. Under day-to-day conditions, the tidal filling and emptying of Buzzards Bay dominates the current patterns outside of the embayment, and as a result the flow bypasses Slocums Embayment. Model results reveal that only under extreme wave conditions (occurring once per year or less) do the currents curve around Barneys Joy Point producing a sediment transport pathway into the embayment. The role of wave conditions, tide and surge was investigated through 36 model scenarios (4 wave height, 3 wave direction and 3 water level scenarios). The amount of sediment deposited in the embayment increases with wave height. However, when taking into account the occurrence frequency of the wave conditions, our results indicate that smaller, more frequent moderate wave events (with a return period of one or two years) cumulatively contribute more sediment to the embayment than the most extreme events (return period 10-50 years). Applying our method to bypassing rates of 29 headlands in Cornwall (King et al., 2021) revealed dominance of smaller, more frequent bypassing events in a large majority (78%) of the scenarios. This is crucial information for coastal managers and the prediction of long-term coastal change, as it shifts the focus from the rare, extreme events to the more frequent, moderate events. Understanding the exact thresholds for sediment bypassing, and their associated occurrence probabilities, is key for robust sediment budget calculations. Headland bypassing studies in other locations have suggested that headland bypassing in microtidal regimes is mostly wave driven (R. McCarroll et al., 2018; Vieira da Silva et al., 2018). However, sediment transport around Barneys Joy Point is heavily influenced by the filling and emptying of Buzzards Bay. Furthermore, a storm surge can significantly increase the amount of sediment entering Slocums Embayment, although the timing between the peak water levels and peak wave conditions can also open a sediment pathway out of the embayment, as illustrated with the realistic storm scenario. This study therefore shows that even in a microtidal regime, headland bypassing is not necessarily wave-driven, and tides and storm surges can influence the net sediment volume change in an embayment.

Open Research Section

The following data was accessed through various public repositories: LIDAR-derived DEMs were downloaded from the NOAA Data Access Viewer (OCM Partners, 2009, 2010, 2013, 2015a, 2015b, 2018); aerial images were accessed through the USGS EarthExplorer (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>) and Google Earth (<https://earth.google.com/web/>); river discharge data is measured at a stream gauge located in Paskamanset River (gauge 01105933, US Geological Survey (2023)); tides and water levels are retrieved from the NOAA tidal station in Newport, RI (station 8452660, <https://tidesandcurrents.noaa.gov/stationhome.html?id=8452660>); wave and wind data are measured at a NDBC offshore station (station 44085 and BUZM3, <https://www.ndbc.noaa.gov/stationpage.php?station=4408>); the bathymetry is based on the NOAA Continuously Updated DEM (CIRES, 2014); and the sediment texture map of Buzzards Bay was downloaded from the USGS Science Data Catalog (Foster et al., 2016). The NACCS model data used as boundary conditions for the model simulations in this study was downloaded from the Coastal Hazards System (Nadal-Caraballo et al., 2020; Cialone et al., 2015). Measurement data used for model validation, as well as the Delft3D model input files and Matlab scripts for pre- and post-processing are uploaded to the repository of 4TU.ResearchData and currently undergoing quality control. The editor and reviewers can already access the dataset via the following private link: <https://tinyurl.com/2ttxpncw> after quality control the dataset will be published with the DOI: doi.org/10.4121/5232674a-4255-465f-bd36-306e9a0a9a97 (Tas et al., 2024). The measurement data includes bathymetry measurements and ADCP wave and current measurements (both collected by WHG as part of this project), grain size distributions of sediment samples, RBR wave data, Nortek AquaDopp water level and current data and HOBO water level data. Delft3D is open-source software developed by Deltares (Lesser et al., 2004). The modelled bypassing rates of King et al. (2021) were accessed through the doi: [10.24382/36902c25-9914-4b55-aabb-ae70c38fe394](https://doi.org/10.24382/36902c25-9914-4b55-aabb-ae70c38fe394).

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